

ASSESSING THE DYNAMICS OF ENERGY ACCESS AND KEY ECONOMIC VARIABLES: A TIME SERIES ANALYSIS: 1990–2023

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Abstract

This study investigates the dynamic relationship between energy access and key macroeconomic indicators in Nigeria from 1990 to 2023 using time series data and the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model. Unlike most studies that assess how energy access drives economic growth, this research reverses the direction of analysis by examining how Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Human Development Index (HDI), Manufacturing Output, and Population influence access to electricity. The results reveal that previous levels of energy access significantly determine current access, indicating persistence over time. GDP has an initial negative effect but turns positive after one year, implying that economic growth takes time to improve energy availability. Manufacturing Output shows a short-term positive but lagged negative effect, while Population exerts a delayed positive influence. The error correction term confirms rapid adjustment toward long-term equilibrium. In the long run, GDP negatively affects energy access, suggesting growth alone does not ensure equitable energy distribution, whereas Manufacturing Output and Population have positive and significant impacts. HDI shows a positive but insignificant effect. Diagnostic tests confirm the model's reliability and stability. The study recommends integrated policies linking economic growth, industrial expansion, and infrastructure investment to promote inclusive and sustainable energy access in Nigeria.

Keywords: Energy Access, Economic Growth, Manufacturing Output, Human Development, ARDL.

INTRODUCTION

Access to reliable and sustainable energy is a critical driver of socio-economic development, particularly in emerging economies like Nigeria. Despite being richly endowed with natural resources such as oil, gas, hydro, and renewable energy sources, Nigeria continues to face persistent challenges in providing affordable and reliable energy for its population and industries. With a population exceeding 200 million and a burgeoning manufacturing sector poised for growth, the country's ability to ensure reliable energy provision is paramount (World Bank, 2022). When it comes to access, the World Energy Outlook 2020 database (IEA, 2020), as published by the International Energy Agency (IEA), placed electricity access in Nigeria at 61.6% as of 2019. However, Remteng, Suleiman, Asoegwu, & Emenyonu, C. N. (2021) shows that the access drops in 2020 due to the effects of COVID-19. Limited energy access constrains industrial productivity, economic growth, and improvements in human welfare. The country's dependence on hydrocarbons, infrastructural deficiencies, and policy inconsistencies have exacerbated the imbalance between growing energy demand and limited supply capacity.

Over the years, several reforms—including the National Energy Policy (1998), the Electric Power Sector Reform Act (2005), the Nigerian Gas Master Plan (2008), and the National Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Policy (2015)—have been implemented to improve efficiency and expand access. However, progress remains limited, with the International

Energy Agency (2020) estimating electricity access at only 61.6% in 2019. This highlights the urgent need to understand how economic and social indicators influence energy accessibility in Nigeria.

This study explores the dynamic relationship between energy access and key macroeconomic variables—Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Human Development Index (HDI), Manufacturing Output (MO), and Population (PO)

The study is guided by the following hypotheses:

H01: There is no significant relationship between Human Development and Energy Access.

H02: There is no significant relationship between Manufacturing Output and Energy Access.

H03: There is no significant relationship between Economic Growth and Energy Access.

H04: There is no causal relationship among Energy Access, Human Development, Manufacturing Output, and Economic Growth.

The importance of this study lies in its theoretical and practical contributions. It adopts a reverse analytical framework—treating energy access as the dependent variable influenced by economic growth indicators—thereby expanding existing literature which often treats energy as the independent variable.

This research contributes to academic and policy discourse by revealing how economic growth, manufacturing output, and population dynamics jointly determine energy access. Its findings will inform policymakers, investors, and development partners on how to align economic strategies with energy sector reforms to promote inclusive and sustainable development. The insights drawn from Nigeria, Africa's most populous nation and largest economy, offer valuable lessons for other developing countries confronting similar challenges of energy poverty and industrial underperformance.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The study employed secondary data covering 1990–2023, sourced from the world development indicators, statista, macrotrends, human development reports, IMF data portal and central bank of Nigeria statistical bulletins. The autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model was used to examine short- and long-run relationships between energy access (EA) and explanatory variables: Gross domestic product (GDP), manufacturing output (MO), human development index (HDI), and population (PO).

In the study we carried out an analysis of trends in variables and summary statistics, Pre-estimation tests such as correlation analysis, unit root (ADF), VAR (Vector Autoregression) Lag Order Selection, Granger causality and cointegration (ARDL bounds test) were conducted, followed by short-run and long-run estimations and post estimation tests such as Normality test, higher order serial correlation and heteroscedasticity test were also carried out. The dependent variable, energy access (EA), represents the percentage of Nigeria's population with access to electricity. The independent variables include the Human Development Index (HDI),

a composite measure of life expectancy, education, and income; Gross Domestic Product (GDP), measured in billions of U.S. dollars; Manufacturing Output (MO), also measured in billions of U.S. dollars, reflecting the contribution of the manufacturing sector; and Population (PO), measured as the total number of residents in Nigeria. The ARDL model is:

$$\Delta EA = \beta_0 + \beta_1 GDP + \beta_2 MO + \beta_3 HDI + \beta_3 PO + \sum_{i=1} \beta_1 GDP + \sum_{i=1} \beta_2 MO + \sum_{i=1} \beta_3 HDI + \sum_{i=1} \beta_3 PO + \mu_{t-1} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where:

- GDP= Gross Domestic Product
- EA= Energy Access
- MO= Manufacturing output
- HDI= Human Development Index
- PO= Population

Before the main estimation, several preliminary analyses were conducted to ensure the reliability and validity of the data. These pre-estimation procedures included descriptive statistics, unit root tests, correlation analysis, and Granger causality tests. Descriptive statistics provided an overview of the dataset by summarizing its central tendencies and dispersion, helping to identify potential outliers or anomalies.

The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) unit root tests were applied to determine the stationarity of the variables, which is essential for avoiding spurious regression results in time series analysis.

Furthermore, correlation analysis was employed to examine the strength and direction of relationships between variables, while the Granger causality test helped to identify possible causal linkages among them. The optimal lag length for the model was determined using the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and the Schwarz Bayesian Criterion (SBC), ensuring model efficiency and accuracy.

The study adopted the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model due to its robustness and flexibility in handling variables integrated at different levels, specifically I(0) and I(1). This approach allows for the simultaneous estimation of both short-run and long-run relationships among variables.

After estimation, a series of post-diagnostic tests were conducted to verify the robustness of the model. The Jarque-Bera test was used to confirm the normality of residuals, while the Durbin-Watson and Breusch-Godfrey tests examined the presence of serial correlation. The Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test was applied to detect any heteroscedasticity in the residuals.

Finally, the Cumulative Sum (CUSUM) and Cumulative Sum of Squares (CUSUMSQ) tests were performed to assess the overall stability of the model. These diagnostic evaluations confirmed that the estimated model was valid, efficient, and stable for reliable policy interpretation.

RESULTS

From Figure 1 below, the first chart, which shows the trend in GDP, shows that it is steadily and consistently going up. This means that the economy has been growing steadily over the years. The second chart, which shows Energy Access (EA) over time, also shows a general upward trend, but there are some bumps along the way. These ups and downs could be due to specific policy changes, infrastructure projects, or problems like fuel shortages or geopolitical issues. The progress of Manufacturing Output (MO), which is growing slowly but steadily. This trend shows that the industry is slowly growing, which could be because of foreign investment, local business owners, or policies that encourage people to buy goods from other countries. The fourth chart shows how the Human Development Index (HDI) has changed over time, and it also goes up. This means that education, health, and income per person are all getting better. This trend's stability shows that there has been a long-term investment in human capital and that the development agenda is maturing

Figure 1: Analysis of trend in variables

Summary Statistics

Table 1: Summary statistics

Statistic	EA	GDP	HDI	MO	PO
Mean	49.00088	5.369261	0.474000	3.213434	18.83180
Median	50.10000	5.687005	0.482000	3.322570	18.84190
Maximum	61.00000	6.352949	0.548000	4.165264	19.22628
Minimum	27.30000	3.952362	0.241000	2.218182	18.37164
Standard Dev.	8.177188	0.820491	0.065285	0.654384	0.253494
Skewness	-0.625193	-0.542482	-1.658606	-0.172327	-0.156352
Kurtosis	2.911601	1.730869	6.528660	1.692307	1.882678
Jarque-Bera	2.029571	3.600958	30.29476	2.362260	1.738832
JB Probability	0.362480	0.165220	0.000000	0.306932	0.419196
Sum	1519.027	166.4471	14.69400	99.61645	583.7858

The descriptive statistics provide an overview of the key variables used in the study. The mean value of energy access (EA) is approximately 49%, indicating that, on average, about half of Nigeria's population had access to electricity over the study period. The minimum value of 27.3% and maximum of 61% reflect gradual progress in energy availability over time. Gross Domestic Product (GDP) recorded an average of 5.37 (in logarithmic form), suggesting steady economic performance with moderate variation. The Human Development Index (HDI) has a mean of 0.47, showing a medium level of human development, while the Manufacturing Output (MO) averaged 3.21, reflecting the sector's moderate contribution to the economy. The population (PO) variable showed a mean of 18.83 (log-transformed), indicating consistent population growth throughout the period.

In terms of data dispersion, the standard deviations across variables are relatively small, implying stability in the data over time. The skewness values are slightly negative for most variables, indicating mild left-skewness, while the kurtosis results show that only HDI is leptokurtic, meaning it has heavier tails compared to a normal distribution. The Jarque-Bera statistics reveal that all variables, except HDI, are approximately normally distributed. Overall, the descriptive analysis suggests that the dataset is well-behaved and suitable for further econometric modeling.

We then move on to the pretests in which we began with the correlation analysis.

Table 2: Correlation Matrix

	EA	GDP	HDI	MO	PO
EA	1.000000	-0.228863	-0.369847	0.161285	-0.338161
GDP	-0.228863	1.000000	0.287680	0.661952	-0.113451
HDI	-0.369847	0.287680	1.000000	0.001939	0.075237
MO	0.161285	0.661952	0.001939	1.000000	-0.271065
PO	-0.338161	-0.113451	0.075237	-0.271065	1.000000

According to the correlation matrix contained in table 2 above, Energy access (EA) has weak negative correlations with GDP (-0.23), human development index (HDI), and population (PO) (-0.34), indicating that population growth, economic development, and economic growth have

not all resulted in better access to energy. On the other hand, GDP has a substantial correlation with MO (0.66) and a modest correlation with HDI (0.29), suggesting that industrial activity is a major force behind both human and economic growth. MO has a negative connection (-0.27) with PO and weak correlations (0.16) with EA, which may indicate that industrial output is under pressure from the population. PO has a limited correlation with every measure, suggesting possible discrepancies between development outcomes and population increase.

Next, we have the Granger Causality Tests. The Granger causality test shows several significant causal relationships. Energy access (EA) is influenced by human development index (HDI) and population (PO). GDP is Granger-caused by HDI, manufacturing output (MO), and PO, indicating strong economic interlinkages. Additionally, MO and PO show bidirectional causality, while HDI and PO also influence each other. Overall, the results suggest mutual and directional relationships among key economic variables and energy access in Nigeria.

Table 3: Pairwise Granger Causality Tests

Null Hypothesis	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
GDP does not Granger Cause EA	32	0.94481	0.4012
EA does not Granger Cause GDP	32	1.74989	0.1929
HDI does not Granger Cause EA	26	4.29582	0.0273
EA does not Granger Cause HDI	26	2.02077	0.1575
MO does not Granger Cause EA	32	0.56067	0.5773
EA does not Granger Cause MO	32	2.31529	0.1180
PO does not Granger Cause EA	32	9.32058	0.0008
EA does not Granger Cause PO	32	0.74385	0.4848
HDI does not Granger Cause GDP	26	4.49383	0.0237
GDP does not Granger Cause HDI	26	6.34880	0.0070
MO does not Granger Cause GDP	32	4.63378	0.0186
GDP does not Granger Cause MO	32	2.81593	0.0775
PO does not Granger Cause GDP	32	3.74814	0.0366
GDP does not Granger Cause PO	32	4.86613	0.0157
MO does not Granger Cause HDI	26	6.49345	0.0064
HDI does not Granger Cause MO	26	1.40184	0.2682
PO does not Granger Cause HDI	26	1.88339	0.1769
HDI does not Granger Cause PO	26	3.72782	0.0412
PO does not Granger Cause MO	32	2.57360	0.0948
MO does not Granger Cause PO	32	9.51095	0.0007

From table 3 above, the granger cause from the analysis shows significant influence of the Human Development Index (HDI) on Energy Access (EA). The results indicate that HDI Granger-causes EA ($p = 0.0273$), suggesting that improvements in human development potentially stimulate economic activity. However, the reverse causality does not hold, implying that economic activity alone may not be sufficient to drive improvements in human development without targeted development policies.

The analysis also reveals a particularly strong relationship between Population (PO) and EA. Population is shown to Granger-cause EA with high significance ($p = 0.0008$); however, this relationship is unidirectional, as EA does not significantly predict Population.

Another finding is the bidirectional causality between Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and HDI. Both GDP Granger-causes HDI ($p = 0.0070$) and HDI Granger-causes GDP ($p = 0.0237$). This mutual relationship suggests a feedback loop in which economic growth contributes to improved human development outcomes, and vice versa. In addition to these relationships, the study finds that Manufacturing Output (MO) Granger-causes both GDP ($p = 0.0186$) and HDI ($p = 0.0064$), reinforcing the importance of industrial and production capacity in shaping both economic output and social development. Interestingly, while Manufacturing Output influences these variables, there is no significant evidence of reverse causality, highlighting the leading role of the manufacturing sector in driving economic and developmental processes.

Furthermore, the Population variable emerges as a key influencer—not only on EA but also on GDP ($p = 0.0366$) and MO ($p = 0.0007$)—while also being affected by HDI ($p = 0.0412$). These findings suggest that demographic dynamics play an integral role in shaping both economic and social outcomes.

In contrast, several relationships show no statistically significant causality. GDP and EA do not influence each other, nor does EA significantly affect Manufacturing Output or Population. These null results are informative in themselves, suggesting that not all economic or social variables are interdependent over the examined timeframe or under the specified lag structure. Then we move on to our Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test for stationarity shown in table 4 below. Energy Access (EA), population (PO), and Human Development Index (HDI) are all stationary at levels, which means they don't require differencing to become so. However, following first differencing, MO (Manufacturing Output), GDP, and GDP (Gross domestic product) become stationary after initially being non-stationary

Table 4: Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test

Variables	Adf Statistic @Levels	Critical Values		Order of Integration	Remarks
EA	-6.752803	1%	-4.262735	I(0)	Stationary @ Levels
		5%	-3.552973		
		10%	-3.209642		
MO	-4.389961	1%	-4.273227	I(1)	Stationary @ First Level
		5%	-3.557759		
		10%	-3.212361		
GDP	-4.897608	1%	-4.273277	I(1)	Stationary @ First Level
		5%	-3.557759		
		10%	-3.212361		
PO	-3.670626	1%	-4.374307	I(0)	Stationary @ Levels
		5%	-3.603202		
		10%	-3.238054		
HDI	-5.670081	1%	-4.323979	I(0)	Stationary @ Levels
		5%	-3.580622		
		10%	-3.225334		

Table 4 above shows the results of the unit root test. Energy Access (EA), population (PO), and Human Development Index (HDI) are all stationary at levels, which means they don't require differencing to become so. However, following first differencing, MO (Manufacturing

Output), GDP, and GDP (Gross domestic product) become stationary after initially being non-stationary.

Table 5: VAR (Vector Autoregression) Lag Order Selection

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	34.04904	NA	7.37e-08	-2.234542	-1.992600	-2.164871
1	275.8013	371.9265	4.41e-15	-18.90779	-17.45614	-18.48977
2	318.5400	49.31396*	1.43e-15*	-20.27231*	-17.61095*	-19.50594*

The VAR (Vector Autoregression) Lag Order Selection Criteria for the variables are shown in Table 5 above. The asterisk (*) indicates that the test favours lag 2, indicating a notable improvement over lag 1. Lag 2 will probably increase model accuracy without sacrificing efficiency.

Table 6: ARDL Bounds Test for Cointegration

Critical Value	Lower Bound value	Upper Bound
1%	3.29	4.37
5%	2.56	3.49
Computed F-statistic: EA= F (GDP, HDI, MO, PO) = 6.390639		

Table 6 above shows the results of the bounds test for the model. The computed F-statistic is 6.390639, which is compared against the critical values for the lower and upper bounds at different significance levels. Since the computed F-statistic (6.39) exceeds the upper bound at all conventional significance levels, this strongly indicates that the null hypothesis of no cointegration can be rejected.

Table 7: ARDL short-run analysis

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(EA(-1))	0.349889	0.140266	2.494468	0.0232
D(GDP)	-8.998723	3.256774	-2.763079	0.0133
D(GDP(-1))	18.83895	4.581174	4.112253	0.0007
D(MO)	7.764316	3.160673	2.456539	0.0251
D(MO(-1))	-20.08661	4.732849	-4.244084	0.0005
D(PO)	-1422.866	1347.514	-1.055919	0.3058
D(PO(-1))	4966.099	1452.722	3.418480	0.0033
CointEq(-1)*	-1.616752	0.229514	-7.044248	0.0000

Table 7 above shows that previous changes in Energy Access still play a role in the present—highlighting a kind of momentum where improvements (or declines) in energy availability tend to carry over from one period to the next.

When it comes to GDP, the results show that a sudden rise in GDP seems to temporarily reduce Energy Access, which might reflect initial disruptions or misalignments in how growth impacts infrastructure. However, the positive and significant effect from the previous period's GDP indicates that, over time, economic growth does support improved energy access—likely as investments and policy measures begin to take effect. Manufacturing Output (MO) also has a mixed short-term impact.

In the immediate term, an increase in manufacturing activity tends to boost energy access. But the lagged effect is strongly negative, suggesting that after an initial surge, manufacturing may place strains on energy infrastructure or create competition for resources, leading to a short-term dip.

As for Population (PO), current changes don't show a significant immediate effect on Energy Access. However, in the following period, the impact becomes strongly positive and significant. This likely reflects the delayed effects of population growth—such as increased demand, infrastructure development, or policy response—on energy distribution and access.

Table 8: ARDL long-run Analysis

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
GDP	-7.381657	2.629421	-2.807332	0.0121
HDI	12.89254	24.53528	0.525470	0.6060
MO	7.456926	2.922275	2.551754	0.0180
PO	34.75170	6.534760	5.317976	0.0001
C	-652.3541	121.7389	-5.358631	0.0001

Table 8 above show long-run ARDL results show that Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Manufacturing Output (MO), and Population (PO) significantly influence Energy Access (EA) over time. Gross Domestic Product has a negative impact, suggesting that economic growth does not automatically lead to wider energy access.

In contrast, Manufacturing Output and Population both have strong positive effects, indicating that industrial expansion and population growth promote improvements in energy availability. The Human Development Index (HDI), although positive, is not statistically significant, implying that its influence may be indirect or more evident in the short run. The negative and significant error correction term confirms the existence of a stable long-run equilibrium relationship among the variables.

Table 9: post estimation tests

Test	Statistic	Probability
Normality Test	1.916221 (Jarque Bera)	0.383617 (Prob)
Higher Order Serial Correlation	3.584766 (F-statistic)	0.0534 (Prob)
Heteroscedasticity Test	0.815156 (F-statistic)	0.6185 (Prob)

Table 9 above shows the results of the post estimation tests. To begin with, the normality test, based on the Jarque-Bera statistic, yields a value of 1.916221 with a p-value of 0.3836. Since the p-value is well above the 0.05 threshold, we fail to reject the null hypothesis of normally distributed residuals. The test for higher-order serial correlation, which checks for the presence of autocorrelation beyond the immediate lag structure, produces an F-statistic of 3.5848 with a p-value of 0.0534.

While this is slightly above the conventional 5% significance level, it is close enough to warrant cautious interpretation. Although technically non-significant, it may hint at marginal autocorrelation in the residuals, and thus further robustness checks or model refinement could be considered.

Finally, the heteroscedasticity test shows an F-statistic of 0.8152 and a p-value of 0.6185, indicating no evidence of heteroscedasticity in the model. This means that the variance of the residuals appears to be constant over time, fulfilling another key assumption of classical regression models and ensuring that the estimated coefficients are efficient.

Figure 2: CUSUM and CUSUM of square

From figure 2 above, The CUSUM (Cumulative Sum) plot tracks cumulative residuals from the regression and compares them against critical boundaries at the 5% significance level. In the graph, the blue line representing the CUSUM statistic remains within the 5% confidence bounds (orange dashed lines) throughout the entire period.

This indicates that there is no structural instability in the model's parameters over time. Also, the CUSUM of Squares test checks for sudden changes in the variance of the model's residuals—which would indicate heteroscedasticity or volatility in how the model fits different parts of the data. Again, the blue line stays well within the 5% significance bands, providing evidence of parameter constancy and no major variance shifts in the model during the tested period.

DISCUSSION

The essence of this research work is to investigate the intricate relationship between energy access and manufacturing output, Human development, population and economic development in Nigeria. The study adopted Energy Access (EA) as the dependent variable, influenced by key developmental indicators: Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Manufacturing Output (MO), Human Development Index (HDI), and Population (PO) as a control variable.

Empirical results show that the short-run ARDL result of Energy Access (EA) responds dynamically to changes in the explanatory variables. Past changes in EA significantly influence current levels.

A sudden rise in GDP initially leads to a temporary decline in energy access, possibly due to short-term disruptions in infrastructure or policy misalignment, but prior period GDP positively contributes, reflecting delayed gains. Manufacturing Output (MO) shows a mixed effect—positively influencing EA immediately, but with a negative lagged impact.

Population (PO) does not affect EA contemporaneously, but its lagged impact is significantly positive, indicating delayed responses to demographic pressures. HDI's short-run effect is minimal, reinforcing that institutional and human development improvements require time to translate into energy access gains.

Also, in the long-run, there is results reveal that GDP, Manufacturing Output (MO), and Population (PO) significantly influence Energy Access (EA), but not always as expected. GDP shows a negative and significant effect on Energy Access (EA), suggesting that economic growth may not automatically improve access. MO has a positive and significant impact, indicating that industrial expansion drives improvements in energy infrastructure and availability.

Population also has a strong positive effect, likely reflecting urbanization and the policy pressure to scale up energy access as demand rises. HDI, while positively signed, is not statistically significant, implying that human development alone does not strongly predict long-term changes in energy access

CONCLUSION

This study set out to investigate the relationships between energy access and manufacturing output and economic development in Nigeria. On data spanning 1990 to 2023, the research employed an ARDL (Autoregressive Distributed Lag) approach to explore both short- and long-term dynamics, focusing on how variables such as Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Manufacturing Output (MO), Human Development Index (HDI), and Population (PO) interact with Energy Access (EA). The study reversed the conventional energy-led growth hypothesis by proposing that economic and structural conditions actually determine energy access, especially in low- and middle-income countries like Nigeria. The results from this study show several important and sometimes unexpected relationships between the variables.

The study concludes that GDP, manufacturing output, and population significantly influence energy access in Nigeria. Economic growth alone is insufficient to ensure equitable energy distribution; thus, policies must target infrastructure and inclusive access. Integrating human capital development with energy reforms will enhance sustainable growth. Nigeria has a wealth of energy resources, but turning those resources into widespread, reliable, and affordable access for its people remains a significant challenge. Meeting that challenge will require not just more technology or production, but also better planning, stronger institutions, and focused efforts to include all parts of the population in the benefits of energy development.

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Conflicts of Interest

None for the content of this study.

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APPENDICIES

Appendix A: Correlation Analysis

	EA	GDP	HDI	MO	PO
EA	1.000000	-0.228863	-0.369847	0.161285	-0.338161
GDP	-0.228863	1.000000	0.287680	0.661952	-0.113451
HDI	-0.369847	0.287680	1.000000	0.001939	0.075237
MO	0.161285	0.661952	0.001939	1.000000	-0.271065
PO	-0.338161	-0.113451	0.075237	-0.271065	1.000000

Appendix B: Granger Causality

Pairwise Granger Causality Tests
Date: 05/08/25 Time: 22:28
Sample: 1990 2023
Lags: 2

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
GDP does not Granger Cause EA EA does not Granger Cause GDP	32	0.94481 1.74989	0.4012 0.1929
HDI does not Granger Cause EA EA does not Granger Cause HDI	26	4.29582 2.02077	0.0273 0.1575
MO does not Granger Cause EA EA does not Granger Cause MO	32	0.56067 2.31529	0.5773 0.1180
PO does not Granger Cause EA EA does not Granger Cause PO	32	9.32058 0.74385	0.0008 0.4848
HDI does not Granger Cause GDP GDP does not Granger Cause HDI	26	4.49383 6.34880	0.0237 0.0070
MO does not Granger Cause GDP GDP does not Granger Cause MO	32	4.63378 2.81593	0.0186 0.0775
PO does not Granger Cause GDP GDP does not Granger Cause PO	32	3.74814 4.86613	0.0366 0.0157
MO does not Granger Cause HDI HDI does not Granger Cause MO	26	6.49345 1.40184	0.0064 0.2682
PO does not Granger Cause HDI HDI does not Granger Cause PO	26	1.88339 3.72782	0.1769 0.0412
PO does not Granger Cause MO MO does not Granger Cause PO	32	2.57360 9.51095	0.0948 0.0007

Appendix C: Unit Root Test

Null Hypothesis: EA has a unit root
Exogenous: Constant, Linear Trend
Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=8)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-6.752803	0.0000
Test critical values:		
1% level	-4.262735	
5% level	-3.552973	
10% level	-3.209642	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
Dependent Variable: D(EA)
Method: Least Squares
Date: 07/06/25 Time: 23:54
Sample (adjusted): 1991 2023
Included observations: 33 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
EA(-1)	-1.014306	0.150205	-6.752803	0.0000
C	36.16026	5.145377	7.027718	0.0000
@TREND("1990")	0.777408	0.127527	6.096046	0.0000
R-squared	0.610217	Mean dependent var		1.021212
Adjusted R-squared	0.584232	S.D. dependent var		3.229463
S.E. of regression	2.082361	Akaike info criterion		4.391389
Sum squared resid	130.0868	Schwarz criterion		4.527435
Log likelihood	-69.45792	Hannan-Quinn criter.		4.437165
F-statistic	23.48299	Durbin-Watson stat		2.152128
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000001			

Null Hypothesis: D(MO) has a unit root
Exogenous: Constant, Linear Trend
Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=8)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-4.389961	0.0076
Test critical values:		
1% level	-4.273277	
5% level	-3.557759	
10% level	-3.212361	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
Dependent Variable: D(MO,2)
Method: Least Squares
Date: 07/06/25 Time: 23:55
Sample (adjusted): 1992 2023
Included observations: 32 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(MO(-1))	-0.801794	0.182643	-4.389961	0.0001
C	0.039743	0.121914	0.325992	0.7468
@TREND("1990")	-0.000141	0.006141	-0.022980	0.9818
R-squared	0.399278	Mean dependent var	-0.010334	
Adjusted R-squared	0.357849	S.D. dependent var	0.400254	
S.E. of regression	0.320741	Akaike info criterion	0.652694	
Sum squared resid	2.983367	Schwarz criterion	0.790107	
Log likelihood	-7.443102	Hannan-Quinn criter.	0.698242	
F-statistic	9.637618	Durbin-Watson stat	1.892525	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000618			

Null Hypothesis: D(GDP) has a unit root
Exogenous: Constant, Linear Trend
Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=8)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-4.897608	0.0022
Test critical values:		
1% level	-4.273277	
5% level	-3.557759	
10% level	-3.212361	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
Dependent Variable: D(GDP,2)
Method: Least Squares
Date: 07/06/25 Time: 23:57
Sample (adjusted): 1992 2023
Included observations: 32 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(GDP(-1))	-0.918252	0.187490	-4.897608	0.0000
C	0.126408	0.119170	1.060739	0.2976
@TREND("1990")	-0.004312	0.005943	-0.725596	0.4739
R-squared	0.453554	Mean dependent var	-0.011287	
Adjusted R-squared	0.415868	S.D. dependent var	0.404520	
S.E. of regression	0.309168	Akaike info criterion	0.579199	
Sum squared resid	2.771968	Schwarz criterion	0.716612	
Log likelihood	-6.267182	Hannan-Quinn criter.	0.624747	
F-statistic	12.03510	Durbin-Watson stat	1.964737	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000156			

Null Hypothesis: PO has a unit root
Exogenous: Constant, Linear Trend
Lag Length: 8 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=8)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-3.670626	0.0437
Test critical values:		
1% level	-4.374307	
5% level	-3.603202	
10% level	-3.238054	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
Dependent Variable: D(PO)
Method: Least Squares
Date: 07/06/25 Time: 23:58
Sample (adjusted): 1999 2023
Included observations: 25 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
PO(-1)	-0.155359	0.042325	-3.670626	0.0025
D(PO(-1))	1.694190	0.189178	8.955512	0.0000
D(PO(-2))	-1.637078	0.396006	-4.133974	0.0010
D(PO(-3))	1.827267	0.483114	3.782268	0.0020
D(PO(-4))	-1.566042	0.559622	-2.798391	0.0142
D(PO(-5))	1.508171	0.599626	2.515185	0.0247
D(PO(-6))	-0.626588	0.549918	-1.139420	0.2736
D(PO(-7))	0.096550	0.381321	0.253199	0.8038
D(PO(-8))	0.429942	0.220852	1.946748	0.0719
C	2.831093	0.770709	3.673362	0.0025
@TREND("1990")	0.004050	0.001111	3.646762	0.0026
R-squared	0.993050	Mean dependent var	0.026050	
Adjusted R-squared	0.988086	S.D. dependent var	0.001261	
S.E. of regression	0.000138	Akaike info criterion	-14.64365	
Sum squared resid	2.65E-07	Schwarz criterion	-14.10735	
Log likelihood	194.0457	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-14.49491	
F-statistic	200.0495	Durbin-Watson stat	2.519924	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Null Hypothesis: HDI has a unit root
Exogenous: Constant, Linear Trend
Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=7)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-5.670081	0.0004
Test critical values:		
1% level	-4.323979	
5% level	-3.580622	
10% level	-3.225334	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
Dependent Variable: D(HDI)
Method: Least Squares
Date: 07/06/25 Time: 23:59
Sample (adjusted): 1993 2023
Included observations: 28 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
HDI(-1)	-0.600551	0.105916	-5.670081	0.0000
C	0.242578	0.040575	5.978535	0.0000
@TREND("1990")	0.002759	0.000577	4.781128	0.0001
R-squared	0.602093	Mean dependent var	0.005964	
Adjusted R-squared	0.570261	S.D. dependent var	0.011180	
S.E. of regression	0.007329	Akaike info criterion	-6.892950	
Sum squared resid	0.001343	Schwarz criterion	-6.750214	
Log likelihood	99.50130	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-6.849314	
F-statistic	18.91440	Durbin-Watson stat	1.629147	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000010			

Appendix D: Optimal Lag Selection

VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria
Endogenous variables: EA GDP HDI MO PO
Exogenous variables: C
Date: 05/08/25 Time: 22:20
Sample: 1990 2023
Included observations: 26

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	34.04904	NA	7.37e-08	-2.234542	-1.992600	-2.164871
1	275.8013	371.9265	4.41e-15	-18.90779	-17.45614	-18.48977
2	318.5400	49.31396*	1.43e-15*	-20.27231*	-17.61095*	-19.50594*

* indicates lag order selected by the criterion
LR: sequential modified LR test statistic (each test at 5% level)
FPE: Final prediction error
AIC: Akaike information criterion
SC: Schwarz information criterion
HQ: Hannan-Quinn information criterion

Appendix E: ARDL Bounds Test

F-Bounds Test		Null Hypothesis: No levels relationship			
Test Statistic	Value	Signif.	I(0)	I(1)	
F-statistic	6.390639	10%	2.2	3.09	Asymptotic: n=1000
k	4	5%	2.56	3.49	
		2.5%	2.88	3.87	
		1%	3.29	4.37	

Appendix F: ARDL Error Correction Model (ECM) Regression

ARDL Error Correction Regression
Dependent Variable: D(EA)
Selected Model: ARDL(2, 2, 0, 2, 2)
Case 2: Restricted Constant and No Trend
Date: 05/08/25 Time: 22:34
Sample: 1990 2023
Included observations: 30

ECM Regression Case 2: Restricted Constant and No Trend				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(EA(-1))	0.349889	0.140266	2.494468	0.0232
D(GDP)	-8.998723	3.256774	-2.763079	0.0133
D(GDP(-1))	18.83895	4.581174	4.112253	0.0007
D(MO)	7.764316	3.160673	2.456539	0.0251
D(MO(-1))	-20.08661	4.732849	-4.244084	0.0005
D(PO)	-1422.866	1347.514	-1.055919	0.3058
D(PO(-1))	4966.099	1452.722	3.418480	0.0033
CoIntEq(-1)*	-1.616752	0.229514	-7.044248	0.0000
R-squared	0.810378	Mean dependent var	0.801756	
Adjusted R-squared	0.750044	S.D. dependent var	3.131859	
S.E. of regression	1.565792	Akaike info criterion	3.957839	
Sum squared resid	53.93749	Schwarz criterion	4.331491	
Log likelihood	-51.36758	Hannan-Quinn criter.	4.077373	
Durbin-Watson stat	2.570682			

* p-value incompatible with t-Bounds distribution.

F-Bounds Test		Null Hypothesis: No levels relationship			
Test Statistic	Value	Signif.	I(0)	I(1)	
F-statistic	6.390639	10%	2.2	3.09	Asymptotic: n=1000
k	4	5%	2.56	3.49	
		2.5%	2.88	3.87	
		1%	3.29	4.37	

Appendix G: ARDL Long Run Form

ARDL Long Run Form and Bounds Test
 Dependent Variable: D(EA)
 Selected Model: ARDL(2, 2, 0, 2, 2)
 Case 2: Restricted Constant and No Trend
 Date: 05/08/25 Time: 22:40
 Sample: 1990 2023
 Included observations: 30

Conditional Error Correction Regression				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-1054.694	228.8493	-4.608683	0.0003
EA(-1)*	-1.616752	0.297122	-5.441370	0.0000
GDP(-1)	-11.93431	4.258229	-2.802646	0.0122
HDI**	20.84427	41.24351	0.505395	0.6198
MO(-1)	12.05599	4.623372	2.607619	0.0184
PO(-1)	56.18483	12.13138	4.631365	0.0002
D(EA(-1))	0.349890	0.191196	1.830001	0.0848
D(GDP)	-8.998732	4.456814	-2.019095	0.0595
D(GDP(-1))	18.83895	6.073131	3.102016	0.0065
D(MO)	7.764324	4.216267	1.841516	0.0831
D(MO(-1))	-20.08661	6.214179	-3.232384	0.0049
D(PO)	-1422.876	1998.241	-0.712064	0.4861
D(PO(-1))	4966.108	2052.322	2.419750	0.0270

* p-value incompatible with t-Bounds distribution.
 ** Variable interpreted as $Z = Z(-1) + D(Z)$.

Levels Equation Case 2: Restricted Constant and No Trend				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
GDP	-7.381657	2.629421	-2.807332	0.0121
HDI	12.89254	24.53528	0.525470	0.6060
MO	7.456926	2.922275	2.551754	0.0206
PO	34.75170	6.534760	5.317976	0.0001
C	-652.3541	121.7389	-5.358631	0.0001

$$EC = EA - (-7.3817 * GDP + 12.8925 * HDI + 7.4569 * MO + 34.7517 * PO - 652.3541)$$

Appendix H: Normality Test

Series: Residuals Sample 1992 2023 Observations 30	
Mean	-7.47e-12
Median	-0.047834
Maximum	3.743364
Minimum	-2.809385
Std. Dev.	1.363786
Skewness	0.465636
Kurtosis	3.815911
Jarque-Bera	1.916221
Probability	0.383617

Appendix I: Heteroscedasticity, Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Test

Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey
Null hypothesis: Homoskedasticity

F-statistic	0.815156	Prob. F(10, 19)	0.6185
Obs*R-squared	9.006729	Prob. Chi-Square(10)	0.5315
Scaled explained SS	4.072033	Prob. Chi-Square(10)	0.9440

Test Equation:
Dependent Variable: RESID^2
Method: Least Squares
Date: 05/08/25 Time: 22:43
Sample: 1992 2023
Included observations: 30
Collinear test regressors dropped from specification

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-364.6230	250.8365	-1.453628	0.1624
EA(-1)	-0.402556	0.318380	-1.264387	0.2214
EA(-2)	0.246300	0.308242	0.799046	0.4341
GDP	12.43424	7.290391	1.705566	0.1044
GDP(-1)	-11.95611	10.62530	-1.125249	0.2745
GDP(-2)	-0.089587	9.027456	-0.009924	0.9922
HDI	-59.81458	64.88090	-0.921914	0.3681
MO	-13.30632	6.979575	-1.906466	0.0718
MO(-1)	11.65599	10.62753	1.096773	0.2864
MO(-2)	1.325233	8.914985	0.148652	0.8834
PO	21.33471	14.69581	1.451754	0.1629

R-squared	0.300224	Mean dependent var	1.797916
Adjusted R-squared	-0.068079	S.D. dependent var	3.068602
S.E. of regression	3.171335	Akaike info criterion	5.422757
Sum squared resid	191.0900	Schwarz criterion	5.936530
Log likelihood	-70.34136	Hannan-Quinn criter.	5.587118
F-statistic	0.815156	Durbin-Watson stat	1.833101
Prob(F-statistic)	0.618501		

Appendix J: Higher Order Serial Correlation, Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation Lagrange Multiplier Test

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test:
Null hypothesis: No serial correlation at up to 2 lags

F-statistic	3.584766	Prob. F(2,15)	0.0534
Obs*R-squared	9.701871	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.0078

Test Equation:
Dependent Variable: RESID
Method: ARDL
Date: 05/08/25 Time: 22:42
Sample: 1992 2023
Included observations: 30
Presample and interior missing value lagged residuals set to zero.

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
EA(-1)	0.459098	0.302307	1.518650	0.1496
EA(-2)	0.388190	0.258503	1.501687	0.1539
GDP	1.116329	4.466653	0.249925	0.8060
GDP(-1)	0.440239	7.193310	0.061201	0.9520
GDP(-2)	1.634864	6.094679	0.268244	0.7922
HDI	-33.47515	38.22126	-0.875825	0.3949
MO	-1.522833	4.505897	-0.337964	0.7401
MO(-1)	-0.200804	7.291408	-0.027540	0.9784
MO(-2)	-1.971210	6.224762	-0.316672	0.7559
PO	-938.0747	1805.678	-0.519514	0.6110
PO(-1)	476.7189	3422.347	0.139296	0.8911
PO(-2)	439.6462	1805.815	0.243461	0.8109
C	414.1511	253.4818	1.633849	0.1231
RESID(-1)	-0.940287	0.390166	-2.409964	0.0292
RESID(-2)	-0.559809	0.430863	-1.299275	0.2135

R-squared	0.323396	Mean dependent var	-7.47E-12
Adjusted R-squared	-0.308102	S.D. dependent var	1.363786
S.E. of regression	1.559793	Akaike info criterion	4.033837
Sum squared resid	36.49433	Schwarz criterion	4.734435
Log likelihood	-45.50755	Hannan-Quinn criter.	4.257964
F-statistic	0.512109	Durbin-Watson stat	2.337156
Prob(F-statistic)	0.890607		

Appendix K: Cusum Test

